

INDIAN MONUMENTAL IMAGE CLASSIFICATION USING DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES**Adiba Maniyar¹****Syeda Bibi Javeriya²**^{1,2} Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science, Karnataka State Akkamahadevi Women's University, Vijayapura-586101¹adibamaniyar@gmail.com, ²syedajaveriya84@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

The purpose of artificial intelligence (AI) is to construct machines that behave and function similarly to humans. The deep learning models are utilized for classification of Indian monumental images. This allows for the rapid and efficient classification of monumental images. Monumental classification is considered as a complicated task due to the angle and perspective variations, lighting conditions, architectural similarities and occlusions. For the proposed study, the Indian Heritage Image Retrieval Dataset (IHIRD) is used. The study had employed deep learning methods like CNN, VGG16 and Resnet50 for efficient classification of monumental images. To evaluate the model's performance, the different metrics such as precision, recall, F1 score and validation accuracy are adopted. As a result of exploring various models, it has been concluded that using the IHIRD dataset, the Resnet50 model had achieved accuracy of 94.20%, a precision of 95, a recall of 94 and f1 score of 94. It has been understood that the proposed model Resnet50 has performed well, and efficient for classification and prediction for a variety of images when compared it to the other models

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence, CNN, VGG16, Resnet50.

INTRODUCTION

Monuments have enormous cultural, historical, and sociological value, and each of their many functions adds to their significance. Monuments serve as physical reminders of historical societies, occasions, and accomplishments, assisting present and future generations in comprehending and appreciating their cultural legacy. They honor important historical occurrences, conflicts, or figures that influenced the course of history. They arouse interest and promote historical inquiry.

In essence, monuments inspire progress and solidarity while serving as a bridge between the past, present, and future, reuniting people with their roots. Classification of monumental images is a complicated task due to various consequences angle and perspective variations, lighting conditions, weather and seasonal effects, architectural similarities and Occlusions. To address these challenges, techniques for instance data augmentation, transfer models and normalization are adopted which can enhance the strength and accuracy of deep learning methods for monument classification [1].

From the last few years it has been observed that deep learning techniques has performed tremendous improvements in the realm of computer vision, which enhances for more accurate classification and recognition of visual input by computers. It serves as the foundation for contemporary AI-powered visual systems. Convolution neural networks (CNNs) are an increasingly common category of deep learning methods that have confirmed exceptional performance in work of image recognition, detection of objects and segmentation. The research initiated with adopting basic CNN model, in which less validation accuracy was obtained. Later we had employed transfer learning techniques VGG16 and Resnet50 to achieve better validation accuracy [2].

The research aims the utilization of innovative CNN architectures; VGG 16 and Resnet 50. These deep learning models provided better results with least computation time.

Our research attempts to answer the following questions:

Which hyper-parameters lead to the best performance on the task?

Which deep learning model performs better for achieving high accuracy?

The following research article emphasizes the inadequacies in the present literature by concentrating on the inadequate classification of monumental images. The research article aims to fill the gaps by experimenting with deep learning models, fine tuning hyper-parameters, and applying techniques such as data augmentation to enhance the classification accuracy and strength of the system.

Novelty of the proposed method:

- 1) Working on large dataset which comprises of large number of classes.
- 2) Working on imbalanced image dataset in which few classes are having least no of images.
- 3) Strengthening and improving poor basic CNN model using pre-trained models, which is an effort in improving its classification.

RELATED WORK

Khandelwal [1] et al has demonstrated to make use of convolution neural networks (CNNs) for classification of Indian monuments. It tests a number of CNN designs, including MobileNetV2, InceptionResNetV2, ResNet50, and EfficientNetB1 and B3. Training was done using a dataset of more than 4,000 photos of 24 dissimilar kinds of Indian landmarks. The study focused on changing hyper-parameters including batch size, learning rate, and epochs to raise accuracy. The final model demonstrated the efficacy of the method with training accuracy ranging from 13% with ResNet50 to over 98% with MobileNetV2.

Kaiming He[2] et al has contributed on deep learning model Resnet 50 in order to make training very deep neural networks, which are more difficult to optimize. Instead of using unreferenced functions, it reformulates layers to learn residual functions based on layer inputs. Empirical findings demonstrate that these residual networks outperform earlier models such as VGG and can attain greater accuracy with more depth. The authors first placed in the ILSVRC 2015 classification challenge with a residual network of 152 layers and an error rate of 3.57% on the ImageNet dataset.

The proposed study of Nanda Maulina et al [3] worked on smart tourism. Classifying tourist destinations automatically using data in the form of visitor photos is one use case for smart tourism. Firstly, may have various items and characteristics at one location. Secondly, the architecture of some locations may be identical, making it challenging for the algorithm to categorize them. Using ResNet50, we limited our investigation to Jakartan and Depok tourism destinations and achieved better accuracy.

Ninawe et al [4] has worked on the challenge of identifying monument architecture using machine learning approaches is discussed in the study, with a focus on differentiating between Indian Mughal monuments and cathedrals. It efficiently analyses and categorizes images using Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) and Tensor flow. The study emphasizes the importance of optimal feature descriptors and generalizing the model for new databases. The study highlights how crucial it is to use the best feature descriptors and to adapt the model to new databases. Alberato et al [5] has researched on the MonuMAI framework for image-based architectural style and element analysis of monument facades. It involves the development of the MonuMAI dataset, which facilitates tasks like element detection and style categorization and is rich in expert knowledge. Experiments show that the models perform well in real-world scenarios.

Paolanti et al [6] has addressed the sentiment analysis of Cultural Heritage (CH) photos from social media, especially Instagram, using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs). It compares the sentiment classification performance of these three DCNN architectures: InceptionResNet, VGG16 and ResNet. To assure accuracy, 8472 photos were manually annotated and classified into three sentiment categories: positive, neutral, and negative. The study highlights how crucial sentiment is to improving the value and public perception of cultural heritage buildings. The study of Hesham et al [7] states that monuments are symbols of a nation's pride and heritage. The vital points to be noticed are location, cost, timing, representation. The parameter location is described as selecting the monument's placement is essential. The timing can be explained as selecting the ideal launch time is crucial. The representation is defined as an important comprehend what the monument will represent.

Bhatt et al [8] has suggested approach used a linear Support Vector Machine (SVM) to classify the Indian monuments that tourists had visited and extract features. Preprocessing, feature vector development and classification were the three primary stages of the suggested approach. Canny Edge Detection, Local Binary Pattern, Histogram and Co-occurrence Matrix techniques serve as the foundation for the extracted features. Following the construction of the feature vector, Linear SVM was used for classification.

Amato et al [9] has used KNN classification approaches to tackle the issue of monument recognition in photos. It suggests two innovative methods: one classifies images using the consensus of local feature classifications,

while the other concentrates on local feature-based image similarity. The study also offers a thorough evaluation of several local characteristics and image matching techniques for monument identification.

Gada et al [10] have categorized the renowned Indian monuments around Golden Quadrilateral in this document. A popular Deep Learning architecture has been used to identify the photos with remarkable and timely accuracy. Using a deep learning package, all of the classifier's training computations for a web crawler-generated dataset. The computational load has been reduced through the application of the transfer learning approach. The training set is used to retrain the architecture's final layer. Following complete training, the model is evaluated on a small number of arbitrary images to ascertain its test accuracy.

The research performed by Saini et al [11] has suggested a technique to categorize different monuments according on the characteristics of the monument photos. To extract representations, the most advanced Deep Convolution Neural Networks (DCNN) is employed. The algorithm used is trained using cropped photos of various Indian landmarks that demonstrate the country's cultural and geographic diversity. The trials demonstrate how well the model performs when trained using cropped photos of the different monuments. Using DCNN, an overall classification accuracy of 92.7% was attained for the 100 distinct monuments that were taken into consideration in the dataset.

Hatir et al [12] has suggested the uses artificial neural network (ANN) and deep learning (DL) models to identify stone weathering in cultural heritage locations. It discusses how human mistake in conservation procedures can result in the loss of significant architectural elements. 8598 photos of fresh rock and eight different forms of weathering were gathered from historic buildings in the Konya area for the study. Across all classes, the DL model had superior recall rates, with an accuracy of 99.4% compared to 93.95% for the ANN model.

Kukreja et al [13] has highlighted the historical and cultural significance of India's cultural heritage sites. It offers a deep learning (DL) hybrid model for classifying Indian cultural sites that combines long short-term memory (LSTM) and convolution neural networks (CNNs). For several Indian monuments, the study's binary classification accuracy was 92.37%, while its multi-classification accuracy was 95.89%. The study is to support historians and researchers by promoting heritage monument awareness, protection, and acknowledgement.

Kareem Yaseer et al [14] have researched about how tourism is growing and how it affects historical sites, especially in Egypt, which draws a lot of tourists from abroad. It emphasizes how travel enables people to gain knowledge of many cultures and historical periods. Egypt is a popular travel destination, as seen by the large percentage of respondents who said they would like to go there. The study of Modin Rasheed et al [15] has focused on the importance of monuments as markers of cultural heritage that represent societal beliefs and shared memories is covered in the study. The importance of monuments as markers of cultural heritage that represent societal beliefs and shared memories is covered in the study.

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Dataset Description

The dataset adopted for the research work is the "Indian Heritage Image Retrieval Dataset" acquired on request from IIT Kharagpur, which consists of 105 classes of Indian monuments. Every class of Indian Heritage monument has variable no of images. All the images in the dataset are gathered from three different states West-Bengal, Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh. The collection consists of well-preserved buildings from many parts of the country, includes Bahubali Gomateshwara temple from Shravanabelagola in Karnataka, Surabeshwara Kona from Giddalur in Andhra Pradesh and Lalji temple from Bishnupur in West Bengal. The few sample images from the IHIRD dataset is represented below in figure 1[16].

Figure 1: Few images of monuments from dataset [16]

Data Preprocessing

The various steps undertaken in performing preprocessing is discussed below. Along with the raw dataset, annotation file was also provided which helps in proper labeling of each monument. Every image was grouped into different classes. The total numbers of classes are 105. All images of Lord Ganesha are group into class called as Ganesha as shown in figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Sample class Ganesha from the dataset

The dataset was preprocessed to guarantee excellent reliability and quality. Every monument image undergone a sequence of preprocessing process to improve eminence and eliminate several artifact that might potentially obstruct model’s performance.

The various preprocessing steps are:

Image resizing: Every monumental image has been scaled to 100x100 pixels with a consistent resolution. By ensuring that images contain uniform dimensions, this standardization makes batch processing throughout training of model more effective.

Normalization: The pixel values of monumental images are normalized to range of [0, 1]. The pixel values are scaled from initial range 0-255 to a new range 0-1 by this process. This effectively normalizes the visual data to a consistent range that is better suited for training of model.

In addition to preprocessing, data augmentation technique were adopted to enhance the robustness of the training images. Data augmentation is a technique that involves applying different changes to the training data in sequence to artificially enhance the size and diversity of a dataset. It enhances the generalization of models and decreases the threat of over fitting, particularly when the dataset has less number of images. It uses geometric transformations scaling, cropping, flipping and rotation of images to expand the size of dataset. The subsequent data augmentation methods were applied as shown in Table 1.

Rotation: Monumental images were rotated at random within a predetermined range of angles. This helps the model learn rotational invariance and enhances its capacity to classify images at varied orientations.

Flipping: Monumental images were flipped both vertically and horizontally at random. The flipping process improves the model's capacity for generalization and adds symmetrical variations.

Scaling: Within a predetermined range, the monumental images were resized at random. The model can learn to classify monumental images at various sizes and resolutions with the use of scaling.

Brightness and contrast adjustment: Within a specific range, the images' contrast and brightness were randomly changed. This makes the model more resilient to various image attributes by simulating changes in lighting conditions [17].

Dataset Characteristics	Value
Number of class	105
Total image	11378
Training image	9102
Validation image	2276
Image resolution	100*100 pixels
Preprocessing step	Resizing of Image, Normalization
Data Augumentation	Rotation, Flipping, Scaling, Brightness, and Contrast Adjustment

Table 1: Dataset characteristics along with preprocessing steps and augmentation methods

The table depicts that dataset was preprocessed and augmented was further separated into training and validation sets. The training set comprises of 9102 images whereas the validation set comprises of 2276 images, that was applied to evaluate the models performance and classification capability.

Proposed Work:

Step 1 Data collection: Acquired the dataset of monumental images and performed annotation. All the images of dataset are available in different resolutions

Step 2 Data Preprocessing:

Resize: The images in the dataset is resized to the uniform resolutions 100*100 pixels. Normalize: The scaling of pixel values ranges in the form 0 and 1.

Step 3 Data Augmentation: Perform data augmentation to images such as rotation, scaling, flipping, brightness and contrast adjustment.

Step 4 Data Splitting: Perform the data splitting by dividing the dataset into 80:20. The 80% of images were assigned to training and 20% of images were assigned to testing.

Step 5 Model Training: Perform training and testing to deep learning models using train and test sets.

Step 6 Model Evaluation: Evaluate the performance of the trained models base on metrics accuracy, recall, precision and F1 score.

Step 7 Select Best Model: Select the better performing model base on the evaluation results.

Step 8 Comparison: Perform the comparison of validation accuracy among basic CNN model, and as well as transfer learning models VGG16 and Resnet 80.

Step 9 Predict Monumental Images: Use the deployed model to predict the various images that belong to different classes.

Step 10 Comparison: Perform the comparison of validation accuracy among basic CNN model, and as well as transfer learning models VGG16 and Resnet 80.

Workflow of the proposed work:

The proposed architecture is depicted below in Figure 3. For the IHIRD dataset, the preprocessing and data augmentation was performed. Later split dataset into train as 80% and test as 20%. Perform training and testing to respective models and achieve better accuracy. The performance of models is evaluated on the metrics validation accuracy precision, recall and f1 score. The model was capable to achieve classification and prediction of monuments. The study has obtained very less validation accuracy in the basic CNN architecture of 57.18%. In order to obtain high validation accuracy and to achieve efficiency in monument classification, we had employed transfer learning models VGG16 and Resnet50 and achieved better accuracy.

Figure 3: Block diagram of proposed methodology

Deep Learning Model:

Basic CNN [18]: A specific kind of artificial neural network made for applications like image processing and classification is called a convolution neural network (CNN). CNNs are excellent at spotting patterns and features in images because of their architecture, which records spatial and hierarchical information. Classification is performed using basic CNN model. The input layer is of $100 \times 100 \times 3$, conv of $32 \times 3 \times 3$, max pooling of 2×2 , conv of $64 \times 3 \times 3$, max pooling of 2×2 , conv of $64 \times 3 \times 3$, max pooling of 3×3 . Monument images were reduced to 100×100 pixels before being entered into the corresponding CNNs [18].

VGG 16: The Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford is the name of VGG model, a deep CNN architecture made up of many convolution layers with a 3×3 receptive field each followed by a pooling layer. Convolution layers make up the majority of its 16 weighted layers, which are followed by max-pooling and fully connected layers. The input images for this model are expected to have a shape of 100×100 pixels. This means you are excluding the final fully connected layers (the "top" layers) of the VGG16 model [18].

The breakdown is as follows:

- **Convolutional Layers:** 13
- **Max-Pooling Layers:** 5
- **Fully Connected Layers:** 3
- **Activation Function:** ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit)
- **Final Output Layer:** Softmax (for classification tasks)

Figure 4: VGG16 model

RESNET 50: A deep convolution neural network (CNN) architecture called ResNet-50 (Residual Network with 50 layers) was designed for performing identification and classification of images. ResNet50 employs residual blocks, in which shortcut connections are used to add the input to each block's output, so facilitating the learning of identity mappings, simplifying optimized performance, and addressing the vanishing gradient issue. ResNet-50 consists of 50 layers, including convolution, pooling, and fully connected layers. The depth allows it to learn complex features from images. It has been generally used in classification of images, transfer learning and detection of objects as it balances the computational efficiency and accuracy [2].

Figure 5: Resnet50 model

Model Adaptation and Training process:

Model Adaptation and Training process refer to the method carried out to transform and fine-tune a pre-trained model for a novel and particular task. The concept of hyper-parameter tuning acts as an essential role in maximizing performance of transfer learning models. Concurrently to obtain the better results in the research work, the model's learning rate, batch size, and optimizer selection were adjusted [20].

Learning rate: During gradient updates, the step size is determined by the learning rate. Selecting the suitable learning rate is important as it assures stable convergence.

Batch size: Batch size influences computational performance as well as model generalization. Selecting the appropriate optimal batch size provides a sense of balance between computational performance and stability.

Optimizer: Choosing the suitable optimizer is very essential as it reduces the loss function effectively. For the research study, Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation) is adopted as it provides adapted learning rates dynamically and accelerated convergence.

Epochs: One complete run of the dataset is called an epoch. Select the appropriate epoch as it affects the model performance.

Hyper-parameter	Selected Value
Learning Rate	0.0001
Batch Size	32
Optimizer	Adam
No of epoch	20

Table 2: Model parameters

The Table 2 demonstrates model parameters adopted in the research work optimizer is Adam, learning rate is 0.0001, batch size as 32 and no of epochs are 20.

RESULTS AND EVALUATION METRICS

The software and hardware requirements adopted for implementing proposed work is carried out on Intel(R) with i3 core, RAM is 4.00 GB, operating system is 64-bit and x64-based processor. Python programming language is adopted with jupyter notebook as a platform. The various libraries employed are tensorflow, keras, numpy, matplotlib, pandas and seaborn which significantly helped for achieving better accuracy.

Evaluation Metrics: To estimate the better performance model, evaluation was performed on precision, recall and F-1 score metrics. These metrics were employed to assess the model's performance and provide information about the categorization process's effectiveness [19].

Accuracy: The percentage of accurate prediction among all predictions.

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}}$$

Precision: It defines the how much of all expected positives turn out to be right positive predictions, or true positive predictions.

$$Precision = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

Recall: It is defined as the proportion of true positives correctly identified by the model.

$$Recall = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

F1 Score: It is stated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall, which finds a balance between the two.

$$F1 \text{ score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Model Performance:

The evaluation metrics demonstrates that CNN, VGG16 and Resnet50 model's strong performance yields better classification of Indian monumental images. The CNN model yields precision as 57, recall as 57, F1-score as 57

and validation accuracy 57.51%. The VGG16 model yields precision of 93, recall of 93, f1-score of 93 and validation accuracy of 92.75%. The Resnet50 model yields precision of 95, recall of 94, F1-score of 94 and validation accuracy of 94.20%.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Validation Loss	Validation Accuracy
Basic CNN	58	57	57	7.3163	57.51
VGG 16	93	93	93	0.3340	92.75
Resnet 50	95	94	94	0.2613	94.20

Table 3: Classification results accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score

The Table 3 depicts among all deep learning models Resnet50 yields better validation accuracy of 94.20% with precision 95, recall 94, F1-score 94. The model is considered as efficient and robust for performing classification and prediction.

Finally, the Resnet model prediction capability stated that it has ability to accurately categorize almost all the test set images. The snippet of the code and prediction of the image is depicted in below in figure 6.

Figure 6: Snippet of code for Prediction of Elephant image using Resnet50

Analysis of Experimental results and discussion

The validation accuracy obtained in CNN, VGG16 and Resnet50 is represented as graph as shown in figure 7 below. The figure 7a represents accuracy for CNN, the figure 7b represents accuracy for VGG16 and the figure 7c represents accuracy for Resnet50.

7a. Accuracy for CNN

7b. Accuracy for VGG16

7c. Accuracy for Resnet model

Figure 7: Validation accuracy curve of CNN, VGG16 and Resnet50 model respectively

The loss curve obtained for CNN, VGG16 and Resnet50 model is represented in the form of graph as shown below in the Figure 8. The figure 8a shows loss of CNN model, figure 8b shows loss of VGG16 model and figure 8c shows loss of Resnet50 model.

8a. Loss of CNN model

8b. Loss of VGG16 model

8c. Loss of Resnet50 model

Figure 8: Loss Curves of CNN, VGG16 and Resnet50 model respectively

CONCLUSION

Deep learning model have tremendous impact in performing classification. The novelty of the study lies in handling large imbalanced dataset by using data augmentation techniques. The goal of the proposed study is to build up a model that is capable to classify monumental images efficiently. The research work is initiated with implementing basic CNN architecture which achieved less validation accuracy of 57.18%, in order to achieve better validation accuracy, the transfer learning models were adopted. Transfer learning enables models to drastically cut down the time required for training thereby it improves accuracy and generalization. The study

was performed on 11378 images that are obtained after data augmentation. After applying transfer learning models such as VGG16 and Resnet50, the better validation accuracy was achieved. The VGG16 has obtained validation accuracy of 92.75%. The Resnet50 model has achieved validation accuracy of 94.20%. Finally, it has been concluded that Resnet50 has performed better on a large dataset and with less number of epochs. When compared to basic CNN architecture and VGG16, the Resnet50 has outperformed well and was successful in predicting the monumental images.

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